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CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2020101843

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 9 September 2020, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

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Title of invention:

A SYSTEM MONITORING FOR HARVESTING OF FARMING USING DRONE TECHNOLOGY

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Term of Patent:

Dated this 9th day of September 2020

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

This data, for application number 2020101843, is current as of 2020-09-30 21:00 AEST

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Eight years from 15 August 2020

NOTE: This Innovation Patent cannot be enforced unless and until it has been examined by the Commissioner of Patents and a Certificate of Examination has been issued. See sections 120(1A) and 129A of the Patents Act 1990, set out on the reverse of this document.

Dated this 9th day of September 2020

Commissioner of Patents

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